

Chemical Components of *Cassia didymobotrya* Fresem.

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The literature reports some work on leaves and pods of *Cassia didymobotrya* (Leguminosae). Here we report our results on the chemical examination of stems of this plant wherefrom six compounds have been isolated.

Stems of *C. didymobotrya* (3 kg) were chopped into small pieces and air-dried. The extraction was carried out with hot MeOH. The extract on removal of the solvent was chromatographed over silica gel column and elution with a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 3) afforded chrysophanol (1; 7 mg), myricyl alcohol (2; 15 mg), physcion (3; 8 mg) and β -sitosterol (4; 70 mg). Apigenin (5; 10 mg) was obtained after elution with EtOAc-C₆H₆ (1 : 9). When the eluate was EtOAc-C₆H₆ (1 : 1), β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside (6; 75 mg) was obtained.

Chrysophanol (1) was crystallised from petroleum ether as orange needles, m.p. 198°; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 228, 257, 277, 287, 429 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 670, 1 620 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 7.03 (1H, br s, H-2), 7.10–8.10 (5 H, m, H-4, H-5, H-6, H-7, H-8), 2.42 (3H, s, Me). It was characterised as chrysophanol^d. Myricyl alcohol (2) was crystallised from benzene as colourless crystals, m.p. 87°; the acetate (Ac₂O/Py) δ (CDCl₃) 4.07 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₂O), 2.07 (3H, s, OAc), 1.33 (56H, s, 28 × CH₂), 0.90 (3H, br s, CH₃). It was settled as myricyl alcohol⁵. Physcion (3) was crystallised from benzene as orange needles, m.p. 206°; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 257, 266, 288 431 nm; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 400, 1 615, 1 615 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 12.71 (1H, s, OH), 12.51 (1H, s, OH), 7.75 (1H, br s, H-4), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-5), 7.20 (1H, br s, H-2), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-7); 3.97 (3H, s, OMe), 2.47 (3H, s, Me). It was identified as physcion⁴. β -Sitosterol (4) was crystallised from benzene as shining white needles, m.p. 137°; responded to Liebermann-Burchard reaction; its acetate δ (CDCl₃) 5.23 (1H, br s, H-6), 5.00

(1H, br s, H-3), 1.98 (3H, s, OAc), 2.23–0.66 (47H, m, 7 × CH, 11 × CH₂, 6 × CH₃). It was characterised as β -sitosterol³. Apigenin (5) was crystallised from EtOAc, m.p. 346–48°; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 269, 230 nm; δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 7.93 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.03 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.50 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.27 (1H, s, H-3). It was settled as apigenin⁶. β -Sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside (6) was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 280°; responded to Liebermann-Burchard reaction; gave a positive Molisch test; its aglycone and sugar were identical with authentic samples of β -sitosterol and β -D-glucose respectively. It was characterised as β -sitosteryl- β -D-glucoside³.

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